

The Ethic of Care as a Uniting Factor in Leadership Education

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Abstract

Educational leaders must face moral dilemmas in their decision-making process. The ethic of care has been one of the ethical paradigms to solve these dilemmas in leadership education. Several studies suggested that the use of the ethic of care can guide to improved students' satisfaction, academic performance, and discipline problems. This article aims to investigate the ethic of care and its repercussions on leadership education through a uniting outlook. The main objectives of this study are (a) evaluating the question of ethical dilemmas; (b) examining the concept of the ethic of care; (c) establishing a uniting perspective on leadership education; (d) investigating caring leadership as a model of ethical leadership in education; (e) reviewing previous studies on the ethic of care; and (f) attaining a series of conclusions on the use of the ethic of care in leadership education. The review of the literature shows that the implementation of the ethic of care in leadership education promotes empathy, motivation, productivity, collaboration, and unity among members of school communities.

Keywords: the ethic of care; moral dilemmas; ethical educational leadership; caring leadership.

Introduction

We are immersed into the second decade of the 21st Century. It seems that from the beginning of time, we as human beings have not learned much from our mistakes. Or at least, enough to build a world where many of the crises that exist today would not take place. We live in an era where knowledge is easily accessible to almost everybody; globally, the literacy rate is high; technology has developed in ways we cannot imagine. However, this world is inundated with crises: pandemics, wars, poverty, injustice, corruption, ethical scandals, etc. What is happening with the world? What has changed from the beginning of times to these days? It is obvious that during these centuries, progress has taken place in areas such as industry, commerce, communications, transportation, etc. Therefore, it is important to address these fundamental questions: where is the progress among us, as human beings? Can we state that humanity has progressed? Have we progressed in the way we talk, interact, listen, understand, respect, and help one another? Are we more united or divided with the passing of time? Has there been progress in terms of values and ethics?

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Times change. People change. Industry and technology change. Many things around us keep changing. Leaders advance those changes. Leaders are responsible for designing and implementing those changes. They create a culture with their decisions. Ethical leaders make sure those changes are in the right direction and sustained over a series of moral values. These leaders are passionate about making people's lives better. Leaders that cannot stop referring to those values. Leaders who care about people, about the world. We need these leaders. The world needs these leaders.

This study focuses on ethical schools whose learners are getting ready to carry out their crafts. These learners are about to be our doctors, teachers, architects, lawyers, engineers, etc.

Considering the above-mentioned state of the world, another question arises: is it enough to fill the minds of these learners to fulfil the educational duties or, would it be necessary to fill their hearts as well? Different authors (Grossenbacher and Parkin, 2006) advocate for the need for an ethical approach in education so that our next professionals not only do their jobs with expertise but also guide themselves with the highest moral and ethical standards. Perhaps, that is a way to help this world become a better place. But to instil these moral and ethical standards in learners, first, we need ethical educational leaders who lead by example, leaders who conduct themselves through these ethical paradigms. One of these ethical paradigms is the ethic of care. Keeling (2014) attributes three aspects in presence of the ethic of care: a holistic academic vision; a shared responsibility for learning; and responsiveness to students' well-being. Thus, we need school administrators who care about the people under their leadership, but also learners who care about their own learning. It is precisely the component of "caring" that makes the ethical approach a need. When administrators and teachers care, students feel that care, which makes them come together. That is the reason why we present ethics of care as a uniting factor.

Ethical Dilemmas. The Ethic of Care

In the context of education, ethical dilemmas are situations in which educational leaders confront two or more conflicting moral issues and must choose one over the other.

The English word Ethics comes from the Ancient Greek word *ethicas*, which means relating to one's character. The root word is *ethos* whose meaning is character, moral nature. Dewey (1902) sees ethics as the science that studies conducts and behaviours of people considering these as right or wrong, good, or bad. Viewing this concept from a critical perspective, someone may ask: right or wrong, good, or bad according to whom?

To answer this question, scholars use a system of ethical paradigms. There are several ethical paradigms: justice, care, critique, and profession. In this article, we are focused on the paradigm of care, or the ethic of care to evaluate educational leadership. Leaders in these schools face moral dilemmas in their decision-making process. The ethic of care is one of the paradigms with which ethical leaders try to bring the best solution to the community they serve.

The Ethic of Care

The ethic of care can be described as a newly discovered topic of study in the field of education. Noddings (1984) set up the foundations of this ethical paradigm arguing that caring should be at the heart of the educational system. Soon after, other researchers and scholars joined the effort to investigate this educational construct.

We saw earlier that caring is a prevailing characteristic in ethical schools. Therefore, to be ethical, you need to care for the people around you, the institution you serve, and the subjects and

contents offered to be learned. Following this, in an educational setting, administrators and faculty need to care for themselves, their students, the content, and other individuals of the school community.

Noddings (1992) describes it in these terms: “The first job of the schools is to care for our children” (p. xiv). Noddings (1996) believes in a student-centered educational model where an essential element of the education process is to emotionally support and encourage learners so that the humane side of education is covered. In an ethical educational approach, the ethic of care is not only compatible with the academic side of it, identified often with terms such as “proficiency” or “achievement” but also necessary if we want to avoid the frustration of learners feeling that faculty and administrators don’t care about them (Comer, 1988). For Noddings (1992), the ethic of care comes first when she claims that “caring is the very bedrock of all successful education”, (27). In the contrary sense, any education without caring could never be successful.

In terms of the curriculum, Roland Martin (1993) claims that the ethic of care should be integrated as content in school curriculums. In this sense, Berges-Puyó (2023) shows the benefits of teaching the subject “unity” in schools to enhance understanding of human values such as the ethic of care.

But what is caring? Gordon et al. (1996, xiii) defines caring as “a set of relational practices that foster mutual recognition and realization, growth, development, protection, empowerment, and human community, culture, and possibility”. Taking this definition into account we can stress the following elements pertaining to the ethic of care and their repercussions in an ethical educational model:

A relationship between the “one caring” and “the cared for”. Caring requires a relationship between at least two actors (Noddings, 2013). In the educational setting: teacher and student; and leader and follower. In the first relationship, teacher-student, the teacher is the “one caring”, and students are the ones “cared for”. It is expected that the teacher assumes his role of caring, trying to help his students as much as possible. In this relationship, the teacher takes a proactive role while the student adopts a reactive stand. From the student perspective, this can be detrimental to one of the elements mentioned below: the growth and development of the student.

In the context of an ethical school, we must bring forward the value of responsibility. As we mentioned earlier, Noddings (1984) considers that caring should be a central and pivotal aspect of any school. If someone cares, becomes responsible. The “one caring” role must be mutual and reciprocal if we want effective education to take place in our schools. This also applies in the other relationship: leader and follower. The role of the “one caring” must be present in both leaders and followers if we aim to create schools with high ethical standards.

Mutual recognition and realization. The ethic of care requires a relationship in which the teacher takes the role of “the one caring” and the students take the role of “the cared for”. However, from the perspective of an ethical school, there must be a mutual awareness between the actors involved. This mutual acknowledgment encourages all to assume their own teaching and learning responsibilities (Corno, 1992). Expecting that the role of “the one caring” is unique, exclusive, and one-directional does not help build effective and fair schools since all the learning responsibilities lie in one side of the relationship. In the end, “the one caring” cannot learn for “the one cared for”. Ideally, the inherent caring responsibility (Corno, 1992) of “the one caring” teacher will be enough to help “the one cared for” student see the beauty and enjoyment of the learning process.

Growth and development. As Noddings (1984) claims, one of the goals and consequences of the presence of the ethic of care in education is the students' growth and development. Establishing an ethical caring model in education, students are expected to grow and develop as learners and as citizens immersed in the world around them. From this point of view, growth and development cannot be only measured by the amount of knowledge learners accumulate. Aman (2022) expresses this idea like this:

Learning needs to include progress regarding the insight into what kind of citizen and professional in the job market students aspire to be. Is it sufficient to merely reproduce society and dominant cultural elements or should one aspire to be more transformational and transcendental? What kind of architect, accountant, soldier, politician, or teacher does this individual want to be? What kind of values does this person harbour and what kind of impact does he or she want to make? Such critical reflections at the right level are an essential part of education. (p. 28).

Thus, students understand through those crucial reflections that they are learners but also human beings with an academic and humane role in the world. Through those reflections originated from the assimilation of the ethic of care, their academic and personal development allow them to become not just "the cared for" students but also "the ones caring" for the whole world. Their personal and academic growth puts them in a position where they can see and experience the transformative consequences of that development.

Protection. The implementation of the ethic of care fosters protection at all levels. A caring attitude generates a growth in interest, a push for improvement, an effort to succeed (Lickona, 2004, 2008).

In the educational setting, when leaders, faculty, and students adopt a caring stance, the likelihood of conflicts and crises decreases. People are more focused, committed, positive, and eager to participate. Being caring helps being more empathetic. Therefore, the implementation of the ethic of care promotes the action to provide support for others. This can also be beneficial for the provider, leading to reduced stress, increased happiness, and a sense of social connectedness (Inagaki and Orehek, 2017).

Empowerment. The integration of the ethic of care into the educational experience facilitates the encouragement of "the cared for" by "the one caring" (Noddings, 2013). The implementation of the caring attitude through a series of words or actions generates a larger effect on the receiver: a feeling (Mercado, 1993). In this sense, the caring ethic functions as an inspiration and motivation. As a result, "the cared for" individual gets empowered.

This empowerment experienced by the receiver translates into a process of autonomy and self-determination (Owens and Ennis, 2005) by which the empowered subject becomes stronger and more confident. This strength and confidence inspire him to help others and practice better self-care by acknowledging and responding appropriately to his own emotions, needs and relationships.

This phenomenon of empowerment is possible because there has been a previous process where the spiritual heart has been encouraged. Kouzes and Posner (1999) see celebration and recognition as tools to help in this uplifting mechanism of empowerment. They use these words:

Celebrations are more than parties. They're ceremonies and rituals that create meaning. Public ceremonies crystallize personal commitments, binding people together and letting them know they're not alone. When individuals or teams are singled out for recognition in a public event,

they're held up as role models. By awarding recognition in public to a person who represents the group, you not only give her much appreciated thanks, but you also provide her colleagues with an example they can emulate. (p. 124).

Thus, we see how empowerment is a necessary consequence of inspiring the heart with a caring and loving attitude. But all of that has its genesis in an ethical context that represents the breeding ground in which everything is possible. It is up to us to nurture and embrace that ground. **Human community.** The ethic of care is a uniting factor in our communities because by caring we show our eagerness to project our best in our lives, in the life of others, or in questions regarding life itself. The ethic of care unites us because helps us relate to one another with our whole being. Jarvis (2010) describes it like this:

I know just what you mean. I never saw you as anything more than another student until that moment. In such moments we are surprised by joy. For a fleeting moment we relate fully with our whole being to another person. We are no longer categorizing, we are no longer aside and observing, we are no longer using others or seeing them in terms of their function. We have gone beyond the I-it relationship. We actually meet. (p. 81-82).

Applying care in our school communities helps in strengthening the connection between their members. We don't see labels, categories, stereotypes, roles, but the person, the human being in full display, next to us, with us. Through the ethic of care, we see human beings with human beings. This gives us clarity to understand that we all are the same, forming a whole community made of whole beings in mutual recognition.

Culture. Leaders, faculty, students, etc., make daily decisions in schools. Tsatsou (2011) defines social culture as "a complex set of meanings, habits, values, and behaviours adopted by one or more social formations" (p. 632). When administrators and faculty decide over moral dilemmas in an educational setting, the consistent way to apply those decisions over time creates a specific culture that defines that institution.

Noddings (1984) argues that the key element in education is the ethic of care. This element must define and condition the culture of the entire educational system. Based on this assumption, caring ethics should guide the actions, intentions, principles, and norms of schools.

Creating a caring culture in schools is the first step to establishing a caring culture in society, so that we can build a world founded on caring values whose individuals don't even consider wars, conflicts, corruption, or injustice as an option. If Noddings (1984) claims that we must put the ethic of care at the heart of the educational system, perhaps we should also put values at the heart of societies.

Possibility. Schools sustained upon moral standards offer limitless possibilities for learners to develop both academically and socially. Today, this is more urgent than ever. There seems to be an increasingly paradox: in an era of technological dominance, where knowledge is easily accessible and literacy rate is high, people are getting distanced from those moral values that have helped societies prosper.

Some authors (Baker, 2013; Giroux, 2011; Starratt, 2005) find the justification of the repeated conflicts in a major crisis of values. In this context, the ethic of care in education can be an invaluable instrument to initiate a transformative movement in our schools, helping students realize how essential, uplifting, and encouraging this value is. More than a half century ago, Krishnamurti (1953) encouraged us to initiate this process:

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Only love and right thinking will bring about true revolution, the revolution within ourselves. But how are we to have love? Not through the pursuit of the ideal of love, but only when there is no hatred, when there is no greed, when the sense of self, which is the cause of antagonism, comes to an end. A man who is caught up in the pursuits of exploitation, of greed, of envy, can never love. (p. 48).

Perhaps, this is the moment to start this transformation.

Ethical Leadership in Education

Since the early 90s, several researchers have stressed the convenience for school administrators to nurture an ethical context in their schools (Quick, 1997; Starratt, 1991).

Starratt (1991) called for the need of building schools' ethics on the paradigms of care, justice, and critique.

Campbell (1997) insisted that school administrators would act as ethical specialists.

A few years later, Starratt (2005) suggested that educational leaders would uphold an ethical responsibility and a moral prospect to serve their communities better.

Recently, Shapiro and Stefkovich (2022) supported a multiple ethical paradigms approach in schools, adding a fourth paradigm, the profession paradigm. They showed several case studies in a school setting that present dilemmas coped by educational leaders. At the end of each case, some questions are presented to foster reflection.

Educational institutions are an essential part of our societies. Learners attend schools to get the preparation needed to be successful in life.

From an ethical perspective (Grossenbacher and Parker, 2006; Hare, 2006), being successful cannot be disassociated from learners' moral, personal, spiritual, and social aspects. We are bringing the definition of ethical leadership by Brown et al. (2005), adjusted to the context of this article. Thus, ethical educational leadership can be defined as the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making in the context of an educational institution. Accordingly, we can state that an ethical leader in higher education performs pertinent actions at a personal level as a human being and at an institutional level as a member of that institution with authority in the decision-making process, which produces direct repercussions in connection with students, families, faculty, staff, and other administrators. However, it is not enough to be an ethical educational leader with carrying out moral and ethical actions. Ethical leaders must promote those actions through building relationships with the educational community in a consistent and unchanging manner. Followers and members of the school community must feel they can be heard (Berges-Puyó, 2022) and that the school leaders ensure that ethical conduct is well maintained at the heart of any decision-making process.

Some scholars (Berkovich and Eyal, 2020; Shapiro and Stefkovich, 2022; Starratt, 1991) stressed the importance of the relationship between ethical educational leaders and the upholding

and promotion of multiple ethical paradigms, being one of those, the ethic of care, centre of this study.

Caring School Leadership

The ethic of care is worth considering for scholars and educational leaders. These leaders are responsible for making decisions. In a model of ethical leadership, they are supposed to uphold a series of values and ethical principles in their decision-making process. Thus, the ethic of care is utilized to resolve moral dilemmas. But what is the leadership model that these educational leaders use to resolve these dilemmas? In previous times, leaders were prepared to use the military and business models of leadership, hierarchy-based systems in which commands, orders and instructions were transmitted from the top-down in the organization. These leaders were also in command of their subordinates who were not supposed to share any kind of suggestion, opinion, or idea referring to the institution management (Guthrie, J. W, 1990). They led by rules, protocols, and policies that had to be obeyed. However, according to a model of caring ethics in which diverse options need to be evaluated, this model of leadership to resolve moral dilemmas is unsatisfactory (Shapiro and Stefkovic, 2022).

Beck (1994) and Smylie et al. (2016) argued that it is desirable in a context of moral and ethical decision-making process to leave behind this top-down hierarchical model of leadership and adopt a new one in which aspects such as interactions and collaborations become guiding elements.

In this sense, Barth (1990) introduced the term “head learners”. In a leadership model in which the ethic of care is prevalent it means that leaders and learners are inclined to listen to others at the time to make their moral decisions. Following this, “head leaders” commit themselves to observe, respond, and especially, listen to others. Consequently, followers in an educational setting feel included, since they know their leaders care about what they might have to say and what is more important, feel free to express their true and honest opinions and beliefs.

One relevant aspect in this discussion is the one related to emotions. Educational leaders under the ethic of care act following rational and emotional aspects. These leaders carry out rational behaviours such as providing discipline or being vigilant to students. On the other hand, these leaders demonstrate emotions such as compassion, empathy, patience, or sympathy. In connection with this, Begley (1999) wonders if the ethic of care represents a rational or an emotional model. Some brain research regarding decision-making process (Lehrer, 2009) seems to indicate that the nature of the ethic of care is both rational and emotional which would justify the use of the terms “head leader” (rational aspects) and “caring leader” (emotional aspects). But what is a “caring leader”? Taking into consideration what we have been shown here we can state that a caring leader unites, listens, serves, develops relationships and connections with his faculty, students, and other administrators, and puts the spiritual heart at the centre of the teaching-learning process. A caring leader is encouraging, supportive, and empathetic. These educational leaders make an impact by applying caring and ethical policies to transform schools into learning centers where all members are welcome, safe, and able to fulfil their potential, both academic and personal.

Studies on the Ethic of Care

Several scholars have investigated the development of caring relationships between teachers and students in schools. Dempsey and Noblit (1993) investigated the lack of a caring educational leadership in the closing of a good school for the community.

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Mercado (1993) studied the empowerment component in the ethic of care through school community and collaboration. Mercado concluded that relations of care represent an important influence in learners' academic success.

Tarlow (1996) conducted a study to obtain a useful concept of caring. In her study, Tarlow interviewed 84 participants, members of three different environments: schools, families, and voluntary organizations. From these interviews, Tarlow developed eight characteristics that describe phases of the caring process. These characteristics were providing time, "being there", engaging in conversation, developing sensitivity, acting in the best interest of the other, caring as feeling, caring as doing, and demonstrating reciprocity.

Wentzel (1997) examined adolescents' perceptions of pedagogical caring to their motivation to achieve positive social and academic outcomes in middle school. A sample of 248 students was followed from 6th to 8th grade. Perceived caring from teachers predicted motivational outcomes.

Rogers and Webb (1991) conducted a survey in which students were asked when they perceived teachers as caring. According to the results, students perceived that the teachers were caring when they encourage dialogue, make school fun, provide a safe place for learning, they are sensitive to students' needs and interests, and show concern for students' success.

Phelan, Davidson, and Cao (1991), students declared that they appreciate caring teachers who listen to what they have to say and recognize their academic efforts.

Finally, in another study, Berges-Puyó (2018) found that the more appreciated teachers' behavior by students is kindness.

Conclusion

Following an ethical and moral perspective (Amann, 2022; Mahmoudi et al., 2012), education provides a series of academic and non-academic skills that help students get ready for their professional and personal lives. Considering this approach, leaders in these institutions must prepare learners to face the difficulties and challenges they are going to encounter in the world around them.

Ethical leaders are essential in our schools because they commit themselves to high moral standards (Brown and Treviño, 2006). By following those standards, these leaders become inspiring and effective (Adair, 2005). The school community is inspired when they believe in what their leadership stands for. Ethical educational leaders love their profession, are fair, willing to listen, humble in serving their followers, and caring (Arar, 2017).

The ethic of care is an essential element in ethical leadership. More than ever, our educational institutions need caring leaders, committed to guiding students through moral decisions and inspiring policies. These caring leaders create a culture that supports all community members. This culture promotes an education with the heart that builds the bridges we need to understand one another, create positive relationships, and prevent conflicts, injustice, or divisions.

It is now the moment to make the effort, all together, to try with our caring hearts, to make this world better, peaceful, and united. This study and the following conclusions aim to join this precious endeavor:

(1) Educational leaders face moral dilemmas regularly. These dilemmas are solved by the implementation of ethical paradigms, which are sustained over the pillars of human values: love, compassion, empathy, justice, humility, etc. The way to solve these moral dilemmas maintained

over a period of time, creates a particular culture that defines the vision established by school leaders.

(2) The ethic of care represents one of the ethical paradigms to solve moral dilemmas. Noddings (1984, 1992) considers that the ethic of care should be placed at the heart of any educational system. Specifically, several scholars (Beck, 1994; Keeling, 2014; Noddings, 1984, 2013; Smylie et al., 2016) believe that caring ethics should guide educational aspects such as leadership, teaching-learning, decision-making process, curriculum, relationships, discipline, motivation, etc.

(3) The ethic of care represents a uniting ethical model of education because caring ethics foment positive, collaborative, and empathetic relationships. This ethical paradigm is sustained upon universal values that are shared by all human beings (Amann, 2022).

(4) A caring school leadership shows the need to implement a leadership model based on relationships, interactions, communication, and a propensity to listen to others. A hierarchical top-down model where leaders give commands and followers obey them, differs from a caring leadership approach. A caring school leadership promotes empathy, motivation, productivity, and camaraderie (Berges-Puyó, 2023; Smylie et al. 2016)

(5) Educational leaders have the responsibility and privilege to serve their school communities. Ethical leadership may be an influential factor of motivation, inspiration, and encouragement for students, faculty, and staff, by nurturing a culture of care (Douglass, 2017).

In the world in which we are living, inundated by crises of all kinds, pandemics, wars, poverty, injustice, corruption, ethical scandals, and reduction of fundamental rights such as freedom of speech and others, it is more necessary than ever to promote the ethic of care. How can we explain that in the second decade of the 21st century it seems that the state of the world is worsening so rapidly? How can we explain the number of wars that are lacerating the world? How can we explain the poverty, misery, corruption, and injustice? Perhaps it can be explained in that we don't care enough. Because if we cared enough, those crises would not exist, or at least, in the number they exist today.

For that reason, we stress in this study the importance to create ethical educational systems, where students are taught not only contents, data, academics, etc., but also ways to observe the reality around them, mechanisms to reflect, values and character traits (Orr, 1991; Shapiro, 2010). With those values well integrated in their personal and professional lives, perhaps we would care enough to no longer sponsor wars, and instead, building hospitals, schools, and roads; providing affordable housing, education, drinking water and irrigation systems; and above all, erecting bridges for all human beings so that we would care for one another more.

It is time that school leaders get the resources, preparation and support needed to become ethical leaders and to put the ultimate uniting factor first: the ethic of care. Caring leaders favour caring communities, and caring communities make a caring world. That is the promising path. Then, it is up to all of us to follow that lead.

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